

Lord Mahāvīra and Lord Buddha: An Analytical Appraisal

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Abstract

Mahāvīra was the 24th *Trithankara* (supreme teacher) of Jainism. He was born in a royal family and received all the luxuries. He gave up his luxurious existence to pursue true knowledge. After a vigorous ascetism, he attained liberation and became the omniscient Jina (the spiritual victor). Another exponent, who shared a similar life story with Mahāvīra is the Buddha. He was royal by birth, yet he adopted an ascetic lifestyle to discover the real source of misery. He discovered the true wisdom and became The Buddha (the Enlightened one). Although these two exponents came with distinct religious and philosophical backgrounds, they have a lot in common. With a focus on their parallel personal histories and philosophical viewpoints, the author in this article attempt to demonstrate the similarities between The Mahāvīra and The Buddha.

Keywords: The Mahāvīra, The Buddha, Similarities, life history, Philosophical thoughts, Jainism, Buddhism

Introduction

Lord Mahāvīra and Lord Buddha are eminent philosophers of Indian philosophy, who provided a fresh insight into the socio-religious and philosophical traditions of India. Their thoughts and philosophy influenced scholars from different backgrounds. The great scholar like Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi was inspired by their thoughts and practiced non-violence, which is known as *Ahiṃsā*, in his life. Gandhi's monumental abhorrence of violence

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stemmed from the Jainist and Buddhist infusions into his Hinduism but, particularly, from his love of human beings. (Fischer,1957, pp.288) Besides their influence on the ethical view of Indian society, their non-theistic philosophy changed the picture of Indian philosophy. These two scholars being a practitioner of two different religious traditions, share many commonalities in their life stories and philosophy. The present paper emphasizes more on the parallel life histories and philosophical viewpoints of these two exponents rather than differences. It is structured into two sections: the first part discusses the lives of the two exponents and highlights the similarities between them, and the second part examines the parallel between their philosophical teachings.

Life History of the Mahāvīra and the Buddha

Lord Mahāvīra was the 24th *Trithankara*, who was born in the *Kshatriya* clan. There is a legend that Mahāvīra had two mothers Devānandā and Triśalā, which was written in many texts.¹ He was first conceived in the womb of *Brāhmaṇa* woman Devānandā but was subsequently moved to the womb of kshatriya woman Triśalā. The Digambara account rejects this legend as ‘absurd’ but the *Śvetambaras* strongly uphold its truth. (Chand, 1948, pp.22) His mother experienced fourteen dreams prior to his birth.² One of which was an elephant dream. Digambara accept sixteen dreams. They also assert that she (Mahāvīra’s mother Triśala) witnessed two vases instead of one, filled with pure water. (Jain,1974, pp.33) It symbolizes the child would either become a universal monarch or a prophet processing all the possible knowledges.

Lord Buddha was also a prince, born in the royal family. His mother dreamt an Elephant prior to his birth. Later, Buddha was prophesied by Seven *Brāhmaṇa* that he would either become *Cakravarti* (universal ruler) or the Buddha (the Enlighten one). Nagrajji elaborately wrote on this issue in his book *Āgama aura Tripitaka*. Being a prince of the royal family, they received a proper education in philosophy and religion. Kshatriya clan at that time received more benefits than Brahmins in terms of gaining knowledge as they received knowledge not only on spiritualism but also on philosophy, literature, military, administration, music, and fine arts.

Buddha married a princess holding the name Yasodhara and Mahāvīra to Yashoda. In the *Digambara* tradition (the sky-clad, naked mendicant order), Mahāvīra was celibate till his death and never married but *Śvetāmbara* asserted his marriage. Buddha and

Mahāvīra renounced their home and family to attain spiritual awakening at the age of 29 and 30 respectively. Although Buddha accepted *Madhyama Marga* (Middle path), he practiced extreme physical austerity for six years prior to his enlightenment. Mahāvīra practiced vigorous asceticism to attain *Kevalajñāna* (Enlightenment).

After enlightenment, Mahāvīra and Buddha did not give teaching for weeks. According to the Digambara scriptures, even after obtaining *Kevalajñāna* (Enlightenment) at Jrimbhikagrāma, Mahāvīra did not break his vow of silence taken from the time of *Pravrajyā*, and wandering continuously for sixty-six days in silence, reached Rājagṛiha, the capital of Magadha. (Jain, 1974, pp. 57) Buddha did not give his teachings instantly after enlightenment and stayed in deep meditation. It is stated in *Majjhima Nikāya* “If I (The Buddha) were to teach the Dhamma, others would not understand me, and that would be wearying and troublesome for me.” (Bodhi, 1995, pp.260) Later, they preached their own philosophy and gathered many followers. Mahāvīra and Buddha established their own religious sangha and accepted lay women to become nuns, which made a four-fold division of their followers, monk, nun, lay men, and lay women. They both faced schism in their Sangha, which was created by their relative. Jamāli, the son-in-law of Mahāvīra, caused a schism among Mahāvīra’s followers and Lord Buddha’s cousin Devadatta created a schism in the Buddhist Sangha.

Mahāvīra and Buddha practiced rainy season retreat, Chāturmāsya³ on summer season. Buddhist practiced this retreat for three months and it is known as Varṣāvāsa⁴. At that time, Sangha members remained in a particular location for several months without leaving that location's boundaries and the same practice is present in Jainism, where Jain monks stay at a place for four months. It is known as *Varshayoga*. Buddhist and Jain monks practice this retreat to incur minimum harm to bugs, insects, and other creatures, that are more prevalent during the rainy season.

At the time of these two exponents, religious leaders received strong support and respect from several kings and their kingdoms. Mahāvīra and Buddha, being contemporary of each other, received support from many similar rulers. It is stated in the book *lord Mahavira*, “Śreṇika, the ruler of Magadha, was the husband of the youngest of these princesses, Cellanā, who became a lay follower of Mahāvīra of the Sramanopasak variety.” (Chand,1948, pp.84) This shows that the king’s wife was a follower of Jainism, and the king was aware of Mahāvīra. Śreṇika’s son Kūṇika is represented in the Jain texts as a Jaina.

(Jain,1974, pp. 65) This shows the cordial relation of Mahāvīra with king Śreṇika and his son Kūṇika.

Although there was a strong influence of Mahāvīra on King Śreṇika and his Kūṇika, it would be inappropriate to state that they had no affiliation with other religions. In Buddhism, king Śreṇika and his son Kūṇika are known as King Bimbisāra and Ajātaśatru. These two played very active roles in Buddha's life. It is stated in the book *Lord Mahāvīra and His Times*, "In the Buddhist texts Śreṇika and Kūṇika are known by the names of Bimbisāra and Ajātaśatru and both were devoted to the Buddha. (Jain, 1974, pp.65) It demonstrates that King Śreṇika and his son Kūṇika respected both religions. The indulgence of Mahāvīra and Buddha in the life of the King and his son suggests that the king and his son were Jain but were persuaded to become Buddhists by the influence of the Buddha. Mahāvīra and Buddha had not only shared a cordial relationship with similar rulers, but also shared many similar places for dwelling such as Nālandā, Rājagṛiha, Śrāvasti, Bhadrīkā⁵ and Vaiśālī.

Philosophy and Teaching of the Mahāvīra and the Buddha

In addition to the comparable live histories, Mahāvīra and Buddha also had many similarities in their teachings. One of the main teachings of these two exponents is *Ahimsā*, non-violence, towards all the living beings. They strongly refuted any harm towards living beings. Jainism is the first religious faith in the world which incorporated within it the principles of Ahimsa as a part of its teaching. (Kotturan,1973, pp.11) Jains believe the existence of life not only in humans and animals but also in plants and elements that it should not be harmed. Buddha strongly refuted harm towards sentient beings and his non-violent method influenced people from different religions. As it is stated in the book *Ahimsa: Gautama to Gandhi*, "Though the concept of ahimsa perhaps existed in one form or the other before him, it was only after him (Buddha) that it began to exert a lasting influence on the life and thought of the Indian people." (Kotturan,1973, pp.14) In the teachings of Mahāvīra and Buddha, they showed the principle of non-violence and equal respect to all. They refuted the birth-based division of caste, the authority of the Vedas and animal scarification and focused strongly on birth-based one's Karma.

Mahāvīra and Buddha taught Karma and rebirth theory, where the physical and mental activities lead to the accumulation of karma and continuity towards the next life. They also taught the method of ceasing karma and the rebirth process, which is known as the liberation method. According to Jainism, the practice of five great vows *Ahimsā* (Nonviolence), *Aparigraha* (Non-possessiveness), *Satya* (truth), *Asteya* (Non-stealing)

Brahmacharya (Celibacy) should be done for the attainment of liberation. In Buddhism, Vinaya (rules of conduct) are the foundation of spiritual realization. There is a basic five vows, which are abstaining from killing, stealing, telling lies, sexual activity (celibacy) and intoxicants, which need to be practiced by Buddhist monks and nuns. These five are known as *pañcaśīla* (five precepts) and Jain's five great vows are included in these five precepts.

On the metaphysical level, Mahāvīra and Buddha refute the concept of God as the creator and God's scriptures. They believed that living beings take birth due to their past karma and their karma leads to the next birth. Through liberation, living beings can cease their karmic rebirth. Buddha taught that living beings can attain liberation without caste, class, creed or race distinction. This concept is also accepted by Mahāvīra. But his followers Digambara and Śvetāmbara shared a different view on the liberation of women. The Digambara believed that women could not achieve spiritual liberation because of their gender. She must live an ethical life so that she can be reborn as a man and attain liberation. But Śvetāmbara interpreted Mahāvīra's teaching as encouraging both genders to pursue ascetic life with the possibility of *Kevalajñāna* (*moksha*) by both. Svetambara's concept is closer to the Buddhist concept of the attainment of liberation by any human being.

Jain practices three jewels, *Samyag Darsana* (right intuition), *Samyag Jnana* (right knowledge) and *Samyag caritra* (right conduct) for the attainment of liberation. The entire Jain religion, philosophy and ethics are included in these three jewels. These three are present in the Buddhist eight-fold paths, *Samyag Drsti* (right attitude), *Samyag Sankalpa* (right resolve), *Samyang Vāca* (right speech), *Samyag Karma* (right action), *Samyag Ajiva* (right livelihood), *Samyag Vyāyāma* (right action), *Samyag Smrti* (right thoughts) and *Samyag Samādhi* (right concentration). These eight are also known as *Madhya Marg* (The Middle Path). Jainism accepts five *Jñāna* (valid knowledge), which are *mati-jñāna*, *śruta-jñāna*, *avadhijñāna*, *manaḥparyaya-jñāna* and *kevala-jñāna*. The meaning of these *Jñāna* is accepted by Buddhists.

Even though, Mahāvīra and Buddha focused on the cessation of suffering and attainment of liberation, their concept of liberation is different. Liberation in Jainism is experienced through liberating the soul from the karmic existence as they believe in the concept of *Ātman* (Soul) and on the other side, Buddhists strongly refute the concept of *Ātman* as liberation in Buddhism is attained through no-soul theory (*Anātmavāda*).

Conclusion

Though the Mahāvīra and the Buddha share many similarities in their life history, the author has not come across any description of their interaction. Being contemporary with each other and sharing many similar places for dwelling such as Nālandā, Rājagṛiha, Vaiśālī, it would be difficult to say they were not aware of each other's presence. Buddha's cousin Devadutta was aware of Mahāvīra. It is probably under the influence of Mahavira's teaching that Devadutta insisted on having the five special rules introduced in the Buddhist order. (Jain,1974, pp. 72)

Their parallel life histories influenced their philosophical perspective, that they shared many similarities in their teachings and philosophy. They refuted the authority of Vedas and God as the creator of the world, which gave a strong blow to the Vedic religion that existed prior to them. Although their thoughts correspond with each other to some extent, their main philosophy is different. Buddha, being an asserter of no-soul theory, focused strongly on removing the root cause of suffering, which is *avidyā* (ignorance), whereas Jain focuses on removing Karma through vigorous asceticism and the attainment of liberation by *Ātman*.

Despite these two exponents sharing both parallels and differences, what makes them special is they gave up their opulent princely lifestyles and endured all kinds of adversity to achieve true wisdom. Their life stories have not only given lessons but a ray of hope that we, too can attain perfect bliss if we practice their path. It will be beneficial if we study their philosophy not just for academic purposes but to discover the true purpose of our lives.

Notes & References

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2. Elephant, bull, lion, the goddess Laxmi, garland of flower, moon, sun, a military ensign, a large jar, lotus lake, sea, celestial residence of sages, a collection of pearls and smokeless flame of fire.
3. Chāturmāsya is Sanskrit term, where Chātūr mean four and māsya means month.
4. Sanskrit: Varṣāvāsa Pali : Vassāvāsa, which is means Rainy (summer) season retreat
5. Pali: Bhaddiya. It is also known as Monghyr in modern times.

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